

D1.1 Project handbook and risk management table

Authors:

Francesca Watson – SINTEF
Simon Clark – SINTEF

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Executive Summary

This deliverable sets out the management guidelines which will be followed in the DigiBatt project. The main purpose of the deliverable is to provide guidance to project participants to enable the efficient implementation of the action. The deliverable contains information and links to relevant documents, files and templates to be used in the project, including, where appropriate, links to the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. Information in the legally binding Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement takes precedence over information contained in this handbook. All partners are responsible for fulfilling contractual obligations the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
D1.1 (e.g)	Deliverable 1.1
EB	Executive Board
ECM	Equivalent Circuit Model
EMMO	Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
FMU	Functional Mock-up Unit
GA	General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M1 (e.g.)	Month 1 of the project
MS Teams	Microsoft Teams
MS1 (e.g)	Milestone 1
NTO	Non-technical Objective
PC	Primary Coordinator
PCT	Primary Coordination Team
QA	Quality Assurer
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
RP	Reporting Period
SoC	State of Charge
SoH	State of Health
SoX	State of Health / Charge
TO	Technical Objective
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work package

1. Introduction to the Project Handbook

This handbook is intended to help partners in the DigiBatt project understand:

- How the project is organised
- What their obligations are in the project
- What project management tools are available to help.

The text in this document is taken from:

The Grant Agreement

[The Draft Annotated Grant Agreement](#)

The Consortium Agreement

Links in the document lead to files in the DigiBatt MS Teams shared workspace. If you join the project and need access to the workspace please email the coordinator.

This is a working document which will be updated throughout the duration of the project.

This document is meant as a guide. The definitive requirements in the project are given in the documents linked to above and take precedence over information in this handbook.

All partners are responsible for following requirements in the legally binding Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement linked above.

2. DigiBatt Project Overview

2.1 Summary

The need for clean and sustainable energy-independence is one of the most pressing challenges facing the European Union (EU) today. Building an advanced European battery value chain is essential to achieving this vision while maintaining a robust transport and electricity infrastructure.

Battery supply chains are strained by the need for critical raw materials and recycling, and battery cells must be designed to meet the strict demands of a wide variety of industries including automotive, maritime, aviation, stationary energy storage, etc. Quickly developing new battery designs to meet the diverse needs of many different customers requires a lot of data and testing.

The current paradigm for battery testing is fragmented, time-consuming, and expensive. To fully characterize the performance of a battery cell requires a wide variety of both destructive and non-destructive tests, some of which can last for months or years.

DigiBatt will slingshot the European battery industry forward by developing novel digital approaches to extract more value from fewer tests. This will save valuable time and resources in a highly competitive industry. DigiBatt has assembled a consortium representing some of the world's leading battery research institutions, Gigafactories, and integrators, and will apply recent advances in autonomous battery testing, model-based simulation, and data-driven semantics to promote digital battery testing from TRL 4 to TRL 6.

Overview

DigiBatt will establish a novel, open, multi-scale digital toolbox to accelerate the testing and development of batteries. By STANDARDIZING, AUTOMATING, and ACCELERATING the battery testing process, DigiBatt will streamline testing workflows, improve the quality of results, and make digital battery testing accessible for the entire battery community.

DigiBatt will realise these ambitious goals through:

- Universal, interoperable, semantic data models for battery data and metadata
- Digital twin infrastructure to link experimental testing with model-based virtual testing
- Strategies for intelligent design of experiments to reduce the number and duration of battery tests

Figure 1 The DigiBatt Digital Toolbox

2.2 Objectives and Associated KPIs

Table 1 DigiBatt KPIs and Objectives

Objective	KPI
TO1: Establish universal interoperability of battery testing data and metadata	KPI1: Fully automated exchange of data between physical machines and virtual environments.
TO2: Automate the instantiation of digital twins for battery data analysis and performance predictions	KPI2: Less than 5% RMSE in voltage prediction at beginning of life in an automatically instantiated battery cell digital twin.
TO3: Reduce the duration of battery tests	KPI3: A 30% reduction in battery testing time with less than 5% RMS deviation in extracted quantities between the full-time and reduced-time test.
TO4: Reduce the quantity of battery tests and measurements required	KPI4: A 20% reduction in the quantity of battery characterization tests performed, with less than 5% RMSE in the simulated voltage between a digital twin model parameterized using a full test protocol and a reduced test protocol.
TO5: Improve the reliability of battery lifetime and safety predictions	KPI5: Model-based prediction of the inflection (or knee) point in the battery SoH profile with less than 8% RMSE compared to experiment.

TO6: Establish drop-in simplicity for integrating battery digital twins in system-level infrastructure	KPI6: Co-simulation capability of battery digital twin within a systems-level framework
NTO1: Ensure compliance with the EU battery regulatory framework	KPI7: Compatibility of digital twin framework with Battery Passport specifications.

2.3 Key Facts

- Project number: 101103997
- Project name: DIGITAL SOLUTIONS FOR ACCELERATED BATTERY TESTING
- Project acronym: DigiBatt
- Call: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01
- Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01-07
- Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
- Granting authority: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
- Project starting date: fixed date: 1 January 2024
- Project end date: 31 December 2026
- Project duration: 36 months
- Other projects in same cluster: [AccCellBaT](#), [THOR](#), [FASTEST](#)

2.4 Partners

Information about all consortium members, including links to each partner's website can be found on the Consortium page of the DigiBatt website:

<https://digibattproject.eu/consortium>

2.4.1 Beneficiaries

Full beneficiaries receive funding from the EU for their work in the project.

Table 2 DigiBatt Full Beneficiaries

Acronym	Name	Country	Roles
SINTEF	SINTEF AS	Norway	Coordinator, WP1 Lead, WP2 Lead

DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt	Germany	WP5 Lead
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Belgium	WP7 Lead
VIF	Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH	Austria	Participant
CORVUS	Corvus Energy AS	Norway	Participant
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Juelich	Germany	WP4 Lead
AVL	AVL List GmbH	Austria	WP6 Lead
FREYR	Freyr Battery Norway AS	Norway	Participant

2.4.2 Associated Partners

Associated partners receive funding from other sources for their work in the project.

Table 3 DigiBatt Associated Partners

Acronym	Name	Country	Roles
UOXF	University of Oxford	UK	WP3 Lead

2.5 Budget

The estimated budget for the project is EUR 4,524,762.50 This does not include the budget for associated partner UOXF.

Estimated budget breakdown can be found in Annex 2 - Estimated budget for the action. pdf.

2.6 DigiBatt Timeline

Table 4 DigiBatt Project Dates

Date	1/1/24 – 31/12/26
Duration	3 years
RP1 – Months	M1 – M18
Date	1/1/24 – 30/6/25
RP2 – Months	M19 – M36
Date	1/7/25 – 31/12/26

Figure 2 DigiBatt Gantt Chart

Higher resolution versions of the DigiBatt Gantt Chart can be found in Grant Agreement, Annex 1 - Part B.

2.7 Project Meetings

Meeting schedules for consortium bodies are described in the relevant sections in [Management Structure](#).

2.7.1 Consortium Meetings

Table 5 Consortium Meetings Information

Frequency	Twice a year. The first of these is the Kick-Off meeting.
Location	One meeting per year will be held in person and one meeting per year will be held online. The Kick-Off meeting to be held in Oslo. All other meetings to be held in Brussels.
Participants	Representatives from the whole consortium and other invited guests.
Purpose	To present results and discuss project progress and future plans with the rest of the consortium.

2.7.2 Work Package Meetings

Details about meetings within each work package to be decided on by work package leaders.

2.7.3 Review Meetings

Table 6 Review Meetings Information

Frequency	At the end of each reporting period.
Location	In person, if possible in conjunction with a consortium meeting.
Participants	Representatives from the consortium and from CINEA.
Purpose	To review project progress with the commission and make recommendations for the future.

The first review meeting will be between 15th of August and 15th of September 2025. The first draft of the first periodic report must be delivered to the project officer before the meeting.

The second review meeting will be between 1st of January and 13th of February 2026. The first draft of the second periodic report must be delivered to the project officer before the meeting.

2.7.4 Meeting Schedule

A provisional meeting schedule for the project (subject to change with approval from the Executive Board) is presented in the following table.

Table 7 DigiBatt Meeting Schedule

Date	Host partner	Location	Type
Jan 2024	SINTEF	Oslo	Kick-off
Sep 2024	SINTEF	Online	Consortium Meeting
Mar 2025	SINTEF	Online	Consortium Meeting
Aug/Sep 2025	VUB	Brussels	Consortium Meeting and RP1 Review
Mar 2026	SINTEF	Online	Consortium Meeting
Sep 2026	VUB	Brussels	Consortium Meeting
Jan/Feb 2027	SINTEF	Brussels	RP2 Review

2.8 Personnel

Personnel working in the project can be found in the Contact List on Sharepoint.

2.9 Useful Links

[DigiBatt CORDIS entry](#)

[DigiBatt Website: https://digibattproject.eu/](https://digibattproject.eu/)

[EU Funding and tenders portal](#)

[EU Funding and tenders portal Horizon EU Reference Documents](#)

2.10 DigiBatt Datasheet

The datasheet containing a summary of details about the project can be found on SharePoint entitled DigiBatt_Datasheet.pdf.

This has been extracted from pages 8-12 of Grant Agreement Core.pdf

3. Management Structure

3.1 Overview

According to Section 6.1 of the Consortium Agreement

The organisational structure of the consortium shall comprise the following Consortium Bodies:

- The General Assembly as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium
- The Executive Board as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly
- The Coordinator as the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement

There is also a project officer who is the main point of contact between the consortium and the European Commission.

Figure 3 DigiBatt Management Structure

3.2 Project Officer

The Project Officer's roles and responsibilities are as follows:

- To be the contact point for the consortium
- To have an advisory role
- To ensure proper implementation of the action
- To monitor fulfilment of contractual obligations
- To process periodic reviews and payments

The coordinator will serve as the point of contact for communication between the project officer and the partners.

3.3 Coordinator

DigiBatt will be coordinated by a project coordination team (PCT) led by SINTEF. Dr. Simon Clark will take responsibility for technical coordination and Dr. Francesca Watson will take responsibility for administrative coordination. The PCT, with the assistance of the executive board (EB) comprising WP leaders will deal with the day to day running of the project.

Coordinator roles and responsibilities are set out in section 6.4 of the Consortium Agreement and are as follows:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority
- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7.2 (of the Grant Agreement)
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.
- providing a copy of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes to the Associated Partners.

In addition the coordinator is:

- Accountable to the European Commission for the project.
- The central contact point between the EC and the consortium.
- The representative of all beneficiaries in the project.

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement, Section 6.4.

3.4 Partners

Partner roles and responsibilities are set out in section 4 of the Consortium Agreement.

Project roles and responsibilities for partners are as follows:

- To take part in the efficient implementation of the Project, and to cooperate, perform and fulfil, promptly and on time, all of its obligations under the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement as may be reasonably required from it and in a manner of good faith as prescribed by Belgian law.
- To notify as soon as practically possible the Granting Authority and the other Parties, in accordance with the governance structure of the Project, of any significant information, fact, problem or delay likely to affect the Project.
- To promptly provide all information reasonably required by a Consortium Body or by the Coordinator to carry out its tasks and to responsibly manage the access of its employees to the EU Funding & Tenders Portal.
- To take reasonable measures to ensure the accuracy of any information or materials it supplies to the other Parties.
- To be accountable for their performance and work.
- To draft deliverables and contribute to periodic technical reports.
- To be responsible for their own financial reporting.

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement, Section 4.

3.5 Consortium Bodies

There will be two Consortium Bodies in DigiBatt as shown in Figure 3: the General Assembly and the Executive Board.

Any Party which is appointed to take part in a Consortium Body shall designate one representative (hereinafter referred to as "Member").

Any Member:

- should be present or represented at any meeting;
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting;

and shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

3.5.1 General Assembly

The General Assembly consists of one designated voting member for each partner.

Current members of the General Assembly can be found on Teams in the General channel.

3.5.1.1 General Assembly Meetings

Table 8 General Assembly Meetings Information

Frequency	Once or twice a year.
Location	Online or in person in conjunction with a consortium meeting.
Participants	One voting representative from each partner.
Purpose	To make strategic decisions, assess deliverables and review and mitigate risks in the project.

An extraordinary meeting can be called at any time upon request of the Executive Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly

Table 9 General Assembly Meetings Schedule

	Ordinary Meeting	Extraordinary Meeting
Notice of meeting	45	15
Days before meeting: agenda to be sent out	21	10
Days before meeting: agenda items added	14	7
Days after meeting: minutes sent out	10	10
Days after minutes sent out: to object to minutes	15	15

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement, Sections 6.2 and 6.3.1.

3.5.2 Executive Board

The Executive Board consists of the Coordinator and the Work Package Leaders

Current members of the Executive Board can be found on Teams in the General channel.

Executive Board Meetings

Table 10 Executive Board Meetings Information

Frequency	Once a month on the third Thursday of every month.
Location	Online.
Participants	Work package leaders.
Purpose	To discuss day to day running of the project and keep track of progress and potential risks.

An extraordinary meeting can be called at any time upon request of any Member of the Executive Board.

Table 11 Executive Board Meetings Schedule

	Ordinary Meeting	Extraordinary Meeting
Notice of meeting	14	7
Days before meeting: agenda to be sent out	7	7
Days before meeting: agenda items added	2	2
Days after meeting: minutes sent out	10	10
Days after minutes sent out: to object to minutes	15	15

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement, Sections 6.2 and 6.3.2.

3.6 External Advisory Board

There will be a project advisory board made up of key external stakeholders who will advise on the direction of the project and relevance of results from an industrial perspective.

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement, Section 6.5.

4. Work Package Overview

4.1 Work Package Overview

DigiBatt consists of seven work packages (WPs) with six technical WPs and WP1 for administration, communication, dissemination and exploitation. The six technical WPs can be split into three groups: Digital WPs (WPs 2 and 3), Experimental WPs (WPs 4 and 5) and Applied WPs (WPs 6 and 7).

WP2 will deal with setting up the digital infrastructure required to store and access data in a common format. This will be closely linked to WP3 where the infrastructure for the digital twin model will be created along with new, cell level, physics-based models and workflows for intelligent design of test protocols. Data and methods used to parameterize these models will be generated in WPs 4 and 5.

In WP4 methods to design efficient and targeted safety and ageing testing protocols will be developed. Subsequently a large safety and ageing dataset will be collected in order to parameterize digital safety and lifetime prediction models. WP5 will investigate methods for digital parameter extraction from cells. Parameter sets will be verified and enhanced by accompanying physical tear-down of cells. Digital parameterization of scaled up module level modules (as opposed to cell-level) will also be carried out in this WP.

WPs 6 and 7 deal with the application of the developed models and their verification. WP6 will use the parameterized digital twins from WPs 3, 4 and 5, and reduced order virtual testing models, derived from virtual testing models created in WP3, for accelerated safety and lifetime testing. Digital twins will be integrated into battery management systems in hardware in the loop (HiL) setups to perform online lifetime and safety assessments of real batteries. In WP7 parameterized digital twins and virtual testing models developed in all previous WPs will be scaled up to module and pack level digital twins for electric vehicle and marine applications. The reduction of testing effort and time achieved using tools developed in DigiBatt will be assessed for specific applications and mission profiles.

WPs 4, 5, 6 and 7 will all feed back interface details and specifications to WPs 2 and 3 such that all necessary data and metadata produced matches fields included in the new ontologies and all equipment and models can automatically interface with the digital twin framework.

All WPs will feed results back to WP1 to ensure that communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are successful and thus that the project itself is a success.

The overall work package structure can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 4 DigiBatt Work Package Structure

Table 12 Work Package Leaders

WP	Name	Leader
1	Project Management, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	SINTEF
2	Linked Battery Data Infrastructure	SINTEF
3	Digital Twins and Virtual Testing	UOXF
4	Experimental Design and Testing	FZJ
5	Advanced Characterisation and Model Parameterisation	DLR
6	Model-based safety and lifetime assessment	AVL
7	Cells to systems and validation	VUB

4.2 WP1 Project Management, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

The objective of this WP is to ensure the successful completion of the project overall and successful communication, dissemination and exploitation of project results.

This can be broken down into four sub-objectives:

- Administrative and financial management - including communicating with the EC

- Technical coordination - making sure that the consortium works collaboratively and maximises the expertise and resources available
- Quality assurance and risk management.
- Communication, dissemination and exploitation

Table 13 WP 1 Information

WP Leader	SINTEF
Duration	M1 - M36
Participants	All Partners
Deliverables	D1.1 - Project handbook and risk management table. D1.3 - Initial plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities D1.4 - Innovation and exploitation plan D1.5 - Revised data management plan D1.6 - Final data management plan D1.7 - Final plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities
Milestones	MS1 - Establish online presence

4.3 WP2 Linked Battery Data Infrastructure

The main objective of this work package is to establish the digital infrastructure necessary for creating and exchanging linked battery data in the project. This will enable machine-processing for seamless exchange of data between physical experiments and virtual environments, and ways to share data both internally and with the larger battery community.

This is supported by the sub-objectives:

- Create application ontologies and data models to enable the creation of semantic linked battery data
- Create digital interfaces to exchange data across equipment and models
- Implement a project internal database for automated exchange of experimental and model-based data
- Establish data access methods to support digital twin integration

Table 14 WP2 Information

WP Leader	SINTEF
Duration	M1 - M36
Participants	SINTEF, UOXF, FVUB, VIF, FREYR
Deliverables	D2.1 - Application ontologies D2.2 - Battery model and equipment interfaces D2.3 - Relational database

	D2.4 - Digital twin interface
Milestones	MS2.1 - Successful demonstration of automated data exchange between equipment and linked dataspace MS2.2 - Successful demonstration of linked database access to digital twin

4.4 WP3 Digital Twins and Virtual Testing

The main objective of this WP is to create a digital twin framework for battery cells and systems, focusing on a cell level simulation model. A major part of this WP will involve developing the virtual testing methods to be included in the digital twins. The framework will allow for data access (from WP2) and updating of metadata, experimental data, simulation data and parameters for each digital twin, and will have methods to automate as much as possible workflows for designing specific testing protocols and running virtual tests.

This WP contains the following sub-objectives:

- Setup the digital framework including methods for data exchange with other modules/WPs.
- Develop models of varying complexity for virtual testing and model implementations that support the parameterisation activities of WP5.
- Develop methods to automatically create targeted testing protocols investigating specific processes
- Integrate models and data into the digital twin framework and ensure interoperability and smooth data
- Exchange between different parts of the same digital twin and external applications (e.g. physical testing equipment). Also allowing for co-simulation of the digital twin and the physical battery at the same time

Table 15 WP3 Information

WP Leader	UOXF
Duration	M1 - M36
Participants	SINTEF, UOXF, DLR, CORVUS, FZJ, FREYR
Deliverables	D3.1 - Digital twin framework D3.2 - Virtual testing models D3.3 - Automated testing workflow report D3.4 - Digital twin integration report
Milestones	MS3.1 - Successful demonstration of “closed loop” battery cycling experiments MS3.2 - Successful demonstration of proof-of-concept complete containerised digital twin

4.5 WP4 Experimental Design and Testing

The main objective of this work package is to reduce the number and duration of tests necessary in battery development, using digital approaches.

- Create new approaches and frameworks to accelerate the battery testing in different levels, e.g., cell level, and pack level
- Integration of physics-based models and data-driven models with experimental assessments for accelerated and cost-saving testing
- Evaluating battery performance in real-time while testing and close the loop between evaluation and testing planning
- Conduct the optimised battery testing for characterisation, ageing, and safety assessment in different levels

Table 16 WP4 Information

WP Leader	FZJ
Duration	M1 - M36
Participants	UOXF, VIF, CORVUS, FZJ
Deliverables	D4.1 - Testing plan and facility usage D4.2 - Ageing and safety testing framework D4.3 - Safety results D4.4 - High-throughput ageing results
Milestones	MS4.1 - Defined ageing and safety testing methodology

4.6 WP5 Advanced characterisation and model parameterisation

The main objective of WP5 is the experimental parameterisation of the digital twins developed in WP3 and the development of methods to execute and digitalise the parameter extraction. Ultimately, efficient and universal protocols and tools are developed that reduce time, resources and number of experiments for parameterisation of different types of simulation models.

This will be achieved by the following sub-objectives:

- model-motivated design of experimental and computational workflows based on electrochemical measurements on cell- and electrode-level
- extraction of physiochemical and thermal parameters for physics-based models by cell-tear down, execution of chemistry-lab experiments and use of digital methods for analysis
- non-invasive, on-line parameterisation of performance models for cell- and system-level

Table 17 WP5 Information

WP Leader	DLR
Duration	M1 - M36
Participants	UOXF, DLR, CORVUS, FZJ, AVL
Deliverables	D5.1 - Report on computational framework for non-invasive parameterisation D5.2 - Report on automated, non-invasive parameter extraction D5.3 - Digital parameter extraction protocol D5.4 - Report on pack level models.
Milestones	MS5.1 - Delivery of reference cell parameter set MS5.2 - Successful demonstration of parameterisation by non-invasive approach and cell tear-down

4.7 WP6 Model-based safety and lifetime assessment

The main objective of this work package is to accelerate the accurate assessment of battery cell safety and lifetime assessments, using the methods, tools and data obtained in WPs 2, 3, 4, and 5.

To support this aim, the following sub-objectives are defined for the WP:

- Reduced Order Models regarding lifetime prediction and ageing of battery cells - Faster delivery of information/Parameter on lifetime KPI up to 20% at same prediction quality level or better
- Reduced Order Models regarding safety - Early prediction of lithium plating, thermal runaway and/or other detrimental events
- All models will be able to aid/support in the enhancement of in-use lifetime of battery cells.

Table 18 WP6 Information

WP Leader	AVL
Duration	M1 - M36
Participants	SINTEF, DLR, VUB, CORVUS, AVL, FREYR
Deliverables	D6.1 - Reduced order cell models for lifetime assessment D6.2 - Reduced order cell models for safety assessment D6.3 - Variant management of lifetime and safety model parameters D6.4 - BMS in the loop integration with fault injection
Milestones	MS6.1 - Successful demonstration of lifetime and safety assessment models in digital twin

4.8 WP7 Cells to systems and validation

The overall objective for this work package is to perform Virtual Cells to Systems Validation use-cases on the battery model-in-the-Loop through the following sub-objectives:

- Validating the performance of the battery digital twin in terms of accuracy, uncertainty and tolerance interval using powertrain simulator platforms (e.g., Open vehicle powertrain platform) and system-level Digital Twin platform
- Demonstrating a reduction of required tests and person month involvement up to 25% at the system-level testing for new battery technology and for optimised upscaling of battery from cell to module to pack

Table 19 WP7 Information

WP Leader	VUB
Duration	M9 - M36
Participants	VUB, VIF, CORVUS, AVL
Deliverables	D7.1 - Battery pack upscaling and use-case report D7.2 - System-level digital twin report D7.3 - Virtual battery pack testing report. D7.4 - Critical mission profile selection report D7.5 - System-level battery pack evaluation report.
Milestones	MS7.1 - Successful demonstration of virtual simulator for automotive battery pack testing MS7.2 - Successful demonstration of digital twin for marine applications

5. Deliverables and Reporting

5.1 Preparing and submitting deliverables

Deliverables are described in the Grant Agreement Description of Action Annex A.

Descriptions, responsible partners and due dates can also be found in the DigiBatt_Tasks.xlsx coordination spreadsheet on Sharepoint.

Deliverable production should be overseen by WP leaders.

Each deliverable has a named responsible partner who should coordinate the production and submission of the deliverable in conjunction with the WP lead. Deliverables are a collaborative effort and all relevant partners should assist with production of the deliverable and ensure that the deadlines below are kept.

Deliverable deadlines are final. If a delay is foreseen then the coordinator should be informed as soon as possible.

5.1.1 Deliverable timeline

Table 20 Deliverable Timeline

Time before due date	Action	Responsible
2 months	Assign at least one (preferably two) internal reviewers (QA). Update DigiBatt_Tasks.xlsx worksheet.	WP Lead
3 weeks	Upload draft deliverable to Teams for review. Inform reviewers, WP members and coordinator.	WP Lead
2 weeks	Reviewer to provide comments on deliverable.	QA
1 week	Upload revised deliverable to Teams as a pdf file. Inform reviewers and coordinator.	WP Lead
Due date	Coordinator check deliverable quality and upload to EU portal	PC

5.1.2 Deliverable types

Deliverable types are already defined for each deliverable. See Description of Action Part A, pg 16.

Deliverable type should be stated on each deliverable as indicated in the deliverable template.

For information, possible deliverable types are shown below.

Table 21 Deliverable Types

Abbreviation	Meaning
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.
DMP	Data management plan
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

5.1.3 Deliverable sensitivity levels

Deliverable sensitivity levels are already defined for each deliverable. See Description of Action Part A, pg 16.

The deliverable sensitivity level should be stated on each deliverable as indicated in the deliverable template.

For information, possible deliverable sensitivity levels are shown below.

Public deliverables will automatically be published in the project page in CORDIS.

Table 22 Deliverable Sensitivity Levels

Abbreviation	Meaning
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

5.1.4 Deliverable format

Deliverables should be prepared using the report templates which can be found in the 00_Templates folder on Teams.

If this format is not appropriate for the whole deliverable, a cover page should be filled in and attached to the deliverable.

The template contains various fields which should be filled out. The deliverable information must be the same as given in the Description of Action Part A, pg 16.

Deliverables should be concise and about 20 - 50 pages in length.

Final deliverables should be uploaded to the 03_Deliverables folder in Teams in .pdf format.

Deliverables must be submitted as single file not exceeding 52MB in size.

5.2 Continuous reporting

Continuous reporting is used to monitor progress of the project in the EU portal.

The sequence for continuous reporting is:

1. Participant records communication, dissemination or publication activity in the relevant list linked below.
2. Coordinator updates the portal with entries from the list, roughly once a month.

All the lists linked to below can be found in the tabs at the top of the 08_Continuous_Reporting Teams channel.

Important

The lists must be updated after every **dissemination** activity (e.g. conference presentations etc.), **communication** activity (e.g. press releases etc.) and **publication**.

5.2.1 Dissemination activities

Continuous reporting of dissemination activities should be done in the Dissemination Activities list in the 08_Continuous_Reporting channel on Teams.

5.2.2 Communication activities

Continuous reporting of communication activities should be done in the Communication Activities list in the 08_Continuous_Reporting channel on Teams.

5.2.3 Publications

Continuous reporting of publications should be done in the Publications list in the 08_Continuous_Reporting channel on Teams.

5.2.4 Researchers working in the project

We are also required to keep an updated list of all researchers working in the project. Each partner is responsible for making sure this list is up to date for their own organisation. Please let the coordinator know if you make changes to this list so we can update the information in the portal.

Continuous reporting of researchers working in the project should be done in the Researchers working in project list in the 08_Continuous_Reporting channel on Teams.

5.3 Periodic reporting

Periodic reporting will take place at the end of each reporting period (see [DigiBatt Timeline](#) and [Reporting Schedule](#)).

The periodic report will consist of a print out of all the continuous reporting information in the portal (see [Continuous reporting](#)), in addition to a written text which will follow the reporting template found here: [HEU Periodic Report Template](#).

All partners are responsible for contributing to the periodic report.

For each WP an explanation of the work carried out during the reporting period, including giving details of the work carried out by each beneficiary/affiliated entity involved is required. WP leaders are expected to coordinate report writing for their respective WP.

5.4 Financial Reporting

Financial reporting will take place at the end of each reporting period (see [DigiBatt Timeline](#) and [Reporting Schedule](#)).

Financial reporting is the responsibility of each individual partner. Partners must ensure that all conditions set out in the Grant Agreement, Annotated Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement are followed.

To help point participants in the right direction here are some links:

Information about eligible costs can be found in the [Annotated Grant Agreement, Article 6](#).

Information about the necessary record keeping can be found in the [Annotated Grant Agreement, Article 20](#)

The template for financial reporting which should be filled in by all participants at the end of a reporting period can be found in the Grant Agreement, Annex 4

Important

The information above is not exhaustive. It is each partner's responsibility to follow all rules regarding financial reporting set out in the Grant Agreement, Annotated Grant Agreement and Consortium agreement.

Specific information about payments, in particular about the procedure for recovering excess payments, can be found in the Consortium Agreement, Section 7.

It is generally expected that most partners already have systems in place for correct financial reporting in EU projects. If this is not the case or if you need help with financial reporting, please get in touch with the coordinator and we will try to help.

5.5 Interim Reporting

To reduce pressure at the reporting periods, and to monitor spending in the project we will carry out interim financial reporting every six months of the project (see [Reporting Schedule](#)).

All partners will be required to submit financial reports (as described in [Financial Reporting](#)) for the preceding six month period. These will be used to help produce the financial reports submitted to the commission at the end of the reporting period.

5.6 Reporting Schedule

The provisional reporting schedule for the project is presented in the table below. Internal, interim, financial reporting is planned every 6 months, with official periodic reporting every 18 months.

Table 23 DigiBatt Reporting Schedule

Date	Type	Reporting Period
Jul/Aug 2024	Interim financial report	1st Jan 2024 - 30th Jun 2024
Jan/Feb 2025	Interim financial report	1st Jul 2024 - 31st Dec 2024
Jul/Aug 2025	1st Periodic report	1st Jan 2024 - 30th Jun 2025
Jan/Feb 2026	Interim financial report	1st Jul 2025 - 31st Dec 2025
Jul/Aug 2026	Interim financial report	1st Jan 2026 - 30th Jun 2026
Jan/Feb 2027	2nd Periodic report	1st Jul 2025 - 31st Dec 2026

6. Project Management Tools

6.1 EU Funding and Tenders Portal

The EU Funding and Tenders portal is used by CINEA to manage the project. The portal is used for:

- Storing details of the project (e.g. Project documents, Deliverables, Milestones etc.)
- Storing details of the partners.
- Signing of official documents between partners and the EU.
- Submitting continuous reporting details.
- Submitting deliverables.
- Submitting Periodic Reports.
- Submitting Financial Reports.

To simplify things most updates to the portal will be made by the coordinator with a couple of exceptions:

- Updates to partner details e.g. Changes of name, Changes to researchers working in the project.
- Partner financial reports.

Submitting deliverables, continuous reporting and periodic reporting will be administered in the portal by the coordinator.

In addition to managing the project. Lots of useful information and templates can be found on the portal without needing to be logged in.

The portal can be found here: [EU Funding and Tenders portal](#)

6.2 DigiBatt tasks spreadsheet

The DigiBatt tasks spreadsheet has been setup to monitor status of deliverables and milestones.

Each WP has their own tab with deliverables, milestones and due dates listed.

This should be kept up to date by WP leaders. Names of internal reviewers and deliverable status should also be filled in.

Please **DO NOT** make changes to the structure of the sheet itself. If you want to do this then please make a local copy to use.

For information on the procedure around deliverables please refer to [Preparing and submitting deliverables](#).

The DigiBatt_Tasks.xlsx file can be accessed in the General channel on Teams / SharePoint.

6.2.1 Introduction

In DigiBatt we will use an MS Teams room and attached SharePoint site to communicate and share files. Some types of data may be subject to other procedures for storage and sharing as described in the [Data Management Plan](#).

To request access to the Teams room please email the coordinator.

6.2.2 Channels

There are two types of channels in the Teams room.

6.2.2.1 General project channels

General project channels contain important files and information for coordinating the project. These all start with a number.

Table 24 Teams / SharePoint Channels

Name	Contents
00_Templates	Logos, visual identity, document and presentation templates
01_Meetings	Documents (agenda, minutes, presentations) from consortium meetings (e.g. the Kick-off meeting) and GA meetings.
02_Administration	Contract (Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement), Financial (payment information)
03_Deliverables	Uploaded deliverable files
04_Publications	Uploaded publications coming from the project
05_Communication	Uploaded communications materials (e.g. press releases, flyers etc.)
06_Risks	Risk register excel sheet
07_Presentations	Uploaded conference presentations (and similar)
08_Continuous_Reporting	Continuous reporting lists

6.2.2.2 Work package channels

Work package channels exist for each work package. These are for use by WP leaders and people working in the WPs.

Each channel has the following tabs by default. 1. Posts (chat) 2. Files

The Posts tab can be used to chat with your WP members.

The Files tab lists the files in your WP file space. Files can be accessed, uploaded and downloaded via this tab.

There are also other project management tools which can be added as a tab in each channel. For example a task planner, more lists etc. If WP leaders need anything adding to their teams channel please get in touch with the coordinator.

6.2.3 Lists

Teams lists are used for continuous reporting and the DigiBatt Contact list. They are found in relevant tabs at the top of a teams channel. To add a list item click on + **New** and fill in the relevant fields.

It is also possible to edit the list as a grid. When editing as a grid the list behaves more like a traditional excel spreadsheet where rows can be added and columns can be selected.

6.3 Contact list

The Contact List found in the General channel on Teams is the mailing list which should be used for sending emails.

Steps to send emails are as follows:

1. Click on edit in grid view.
2. Click on filter and filter the list as required.
3. Select the email addresses column in the filtered list and copy and paste into your email.

Figure 5 Contact List Teams Pane

All emails need to be easily connected to the project. Subject lines should start with **[DigiBatt]**.

Partners have responsibility for ensuring this list is kept up to date. If someone leaves the project, please update the `Status` column.

6.4 Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan will be created as part of WP1 in M4. The DMP takes precedence over instructions written in this handbook.

A link to the DMP will be added here once it is created.

7. External Communication

7.1 Dissemination / Exploitation / Communication Plan

The plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities will be created in M6 for D1.3 and revised in M36.

Once ready this page will be updated with the link to the document and subsequent pages in this handbook will be updated with communication requirements for partners.

7.2 Visual identity

Using a common and consistent visual identity in communication and dissemination activities will ensure project results are easily linked back to the project itself and increase awareness of the project.

7.2.1 Templates

7.2.1.1 Slide templates

Presentation templates should be used when presenting work at conferences and other events. There are two main reasons for this: - To ensure consistent visual communication of project activities - To ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement regarding funding acknowledgements and the EU emblem

PowerPoint templates can be found in the 00_Templates folder.

7.2.1.2 Deliverable templates

Templates for deliverables should be used as described in [Deliverable format](#). Word templates can be found in the 00_Templates folder.

7.2.2 DigiBatt Logo

DigiBatt logo files can be found in the 00_Templates folder along with a description and guidelines on how to use the files.

7.2.3 DigiBatt font

DigiBatt fonts used for documents are:

- Windows
 - Bahnschrift (Headings)
 - Open Sans (Body)
- Mac
 - DIN (Headings)
 - Open Sans (Body)

7.3 Website

The DigiBatt website can be found here: <https://digibattproject.eu>.

It is maintained by the coordinator. Please contact the coordinator if you notice any errors or have suggestions for website content.

The website will be updated in accordance with the [Dissemination / Exploitation / Communication Plan](#).

7.4 Social media

Currently DigiBatt has a LinkedIn profile which can be accessed here:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/digibatt/>

It is maintained by the coordinator. Please contact the coordinator if you notice any errors or have suggestions for content.

DigiBatt social media channels will be used in accordance with the [Dissemination / Exploitation / Communication Plan](#).

7.5 Conference presentations

7.5.1 Templates

Presentation templates and visual guidelines for DigiBatt communications can be found in the [Visual Identity](#) section.

7.5.2 Submission procedure

When submitting a conference abstract or presenting at a conference the following points apply:

Table 25 Presentation Notification Schedule

By latest time	Action	Responsible
15 Days before submission	Fill out notice of publication document in the 04_Publications folder and email to coordinator	Publication author
10 Days after receipt of notice	Provide written objections in accordance with the grant agreement to the coordinator and publication authors	Consortium members
1 week after submission	Upload publication to the 07_Presentations folder	Publication author
1 week after submission	Update the Dissemination Activities list in Teams	Publication author

7.5.3 Acknowledgement

All work should acknowledge EU funding as described in section [Acknowledging EU Funding](#).

7.5.4 Reporting

Once presented presentations should be reported as described in section [Continuous reporting](#).

7.5.5 More details

Full and definitive information regarding dissemination of results at conferences can be found in:

[Annotated Grant Agreement, Article 17.4](#)

Consortium Agreement, Section 8.4.2

7.6 Publication

7.6.1 Templates

Presentation templates and visual guidelines for DigiBatt communications can be found in the [Visual Identity](#) section.

7.6.2 Submission procedure

When planning a publication the procedure is as follows:

Table 26 Publication Notification Schedule

By latest time	Action	Responsible
45 Days before submission	Fill out notice of publication document in the 04_Publications folder and email to coordinator	Publication author
20 Days after receipt of notice	Provide written objections in accordance with the grant agreement to the coordinator and publication authors	Consortium members
1 week after submission	Upload publication to the 04_Publications folder	Publication author
1 week after submission	Update the Publications list in Teams	Publication author

7.6.3 Acknowledgement

All work should acknowledge EU funding as described in section [Acknowledging EU Funding](#).

7.6.4 Open-Access

Full rules regarding open-access publishing are laid out in Grant Agreement Annex 5, Article 17

A short summary is given here, please refer to the Grant Agreement for full details.

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements. Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or

equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in *full* open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement. Costs for publication in hybrid journals, where only some articles are open-access will not be reimbursed.

7.6.5 Reporting

Once submitted publications should be reported as described in section [Continuous reporting](#).

7.6.6 More details

Full and definitive information regarding the dissemination of publications can be found in:

[Annotated Grant Agreement, Article 17.4](#)

Consortium Agreement, Section 8.4.2

7.7 Acknowledging EU Funding

Communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

Communication activities should include the “Funded by the European Union” emblem which can be downloaded [here](#).

Any communication or dissemination activity related to DigiBatt must also indicate the disclaimer text in the green box below (translated into local languages where appropriate).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Further details can be found in [Annotated Grant Agreement, Article 17](#).

8. Ethical guidelines

An up to date list of ethical risks and solutions will be maintained during the project and each partner will ensure that all ethical guidelines are followed.

All ethics issues listed in the ethical risks and solutions table will be discussed at general assembly (GA) meetings, twice a year. The GA will ensure that all partners have ethical guidelines and standards in place regarding data management and AI, HSE with respect to battery testing, and waste handling in relation to disposal of battery cells, where applicable.

8.1 Ethical risks and solutions

Table 27 List of ethical risks and solutions

Ethical Risk	Description	Solution
Use of AI on battery test data	DigiBatt aims to apply AI (machine learning) to battery test data to predict future testing outcomes and design targeted testing protocols. This will involve statistical analysis of large datasets of testing data and battery operation data with the aims of achieving the project objectives. Testing data will come from testing carried out within the project and operational data will be provided by industry partners and handled in accordance with the data management plan set out in WP1.	Operational data will not come directly from end-users and will not contain information which can be used to track or profile individual users. It will be stored on a secure server with access restrictions. DigiBatt will adhere to the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI published by the European Commission. However, there will be no use of AI on human data, only data derived from battery simulation and operation.
Disassembly of battery cells	The disassembly of battery cells is planned within the project to support the objective of parameterising the battery digital twin. This activity can pose a potential health and safety risk to the	These risks can be effectively mitigated in appropriately equipped laboratories by adhering to well-established guidelines for performing battery cell disassembly. Within the

	involved personnel, due to exposure to chemicals within the battery.	project, these activities will be conducted by trained specialists and adhere to the HSE requirements for their laboratories.
Disposal of battery cells	The project foresees the testing of large quantities of battery cells, which must be properly disposed of at the end of the activity. Battery cells contain materials that can become potentially harmful to the environment if they are not properly disposed of.	The project will ensure that all appropriate standards for waste handling that are relevant for battery cells are adhered to, such that the materials will not pose a threat to animals or plants in the environment.

9. Risk Register

A risk register has been created to monitor various risks associated with the project are listed below. It is important that any risks which have occurred or may be possible in the future are added to the risk register.

Any risks discovered by a participant should be communicated to the relevant WP leader or the coordinator.

The risk register will be reviewed every month at the Executive Board meeting.

In the case of a risk occurring the risk register should be consulted to check for relevant mitigation measures.

Due to confidentiality issues some items are removed from the risk table below.

The full risk register can be found in the 06_Risks folder on Teams.

Risk No. in portal	Description	Likelihood	Impact	WPs	Proposed Mitigation Measure
2	Data is too complex to be described by current domain ontologies	Low	Medium	All	Work with EMMO developers to extend the domain ontologies as needed
4	Failure to integrate between models and data sub-modules	Medium	Low	2, 3	Ensure interfaces are defined early (D3.1)
6	Accuracy of online parametrization of ECM too low for SOC/SOH estimation.	Medium	Low	3, 6	Focus on more conventional parametrization (more time-consuming, but more robust)
7	No appropriate methods found to accelerate ageing and lifetime testing	Medium	Medium	4	The ageing and lifetime testing will be accelerated by fast manual data analysis and manual updates of the

					Design of Experiment during testing.
8	Appropriate cell field data over lifetime not available	Low	High	6	Wait for cell ageing test results of WP4
9	Safety aspects not fully covered by the parameterized chemistry models	Medium	Medium	3,4,5	Targets defined up front, double checked at M12 in WP3
10	All standard I/O interfaces from HiFi-Elements components are not required	Low	Medium	7	Update the interface and document the interface change (VUB) following EleMA structure: A reference simulation model architecture and interface standard for modeling and testing of electric vehicles.
11	Model-in-the-loop testing connected to IoT and device under test component via FMI/FMUs is not possible	Low	Medium	7	Run a battery model using C-code and/or parameterize the existing battery model (VUB)
12	Lots of similar standards are emerging.	Medium	Medium	2	Need to make sure we collaborate with others.

10. Conclusions

This handbook provides details of procedures and processes which will provide a good reference for project partners and ensure the smooth running of the DigiBatt project. The handbook will be updated on an ongoing basis throughout the project as information changes.

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